

HIGH PERFORMANCE/HIGH RATE COMPOSITE PROCESSING WITH TRAPPED RUBBER

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ABSTRACT

Trapped rubber processing (TRP) is an autoclave alternative to achieving high pressures during polymer matrix composite processing, utilizing thermally induced volume change of a nearly incompressible material inside a closed cavity mould. Recent advances in material and computational technology have made this processing technique more attractive. Computer electronics research has led to the development of elastomers with relatively high thermal conductivity. In addition, recent advances in computer processing have opened the possibility to simulate complex thermomechanical processes with finite element analysis. In this study, the volumetric change and resulting pressure is captured via a series of experiments. These experiments are used to characterize the dynamic in situ change in temperature, the dynamic change in volume and the resulting real-time change in surface pressure at multiple locations throughout the sample. The material characterization includes an iterative testing and computational modelling framework where the design of experiments is fed by initial material models based on the linear coefficient of thermal expansion and then the characterization is improved by the experimental tests. The silicone rubber elastomer used in this initial study was chosen to be compatible with the cure cycle for Hexcel M21 epoxy prepreg system, due to the large amount of material and processing data available. The development of an accurate thermomechanical material model of nearly incompressible elastomeric polymers for use in advanced trapped rubber processing modelling will allow more design freedom with more advanced shapes and less risk of processing failure while maintaining the possibility for custom distributions of pressures and temperatures, therefore, high-quality consolidation during curing.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the demand for carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) increases, the need for autoclave alternatives for high performance composite processing that allows faster throughput while maintaining performance becomes more pronounced. Trapped rubber processing (TRP) is an autoclave alternative to achieving high pressures during the curing process utilizing a temperature induced change in volume of a highly deformable material, such as a low durometer elastomer, Figure 1. Recent advances in material and computational technology have made this processing technique more attractive. Consumer electronics research has led to the development of elastomers doped with additives for increased thermal conductivity. In addition, recent advances in computer processing has opened the possibility to simulate complex thermomechanical processes through finite element analysis in reasonable timeframes. The development of an accurate thermomechanical material model of an elastomeric polymer for use in advanced TRP modelling is the first step in a new field of composite processing research and introduces a new method for more efficient and sustainable manufacturing.

Figure 1: Advanced Trapped Rubber Molding Process.

2 APPROACH

Current autoclave processing of composites relies on polymer compaction through a combination of vacuum bagging and pressurization. The autoclave is heated in a way that increases air temperature and subsequently the surface of the part. This procedure is somewhat inefficient and can take a matter of hours for the part to complete the full cure cycle. Pressurized bladder moulding is another alternative processing technique where the composite preform is placed in a hard cavity mould and pressurized with an internal bladder. This allows for the cure cycle to be reduced to under an hour for thin parts but can be susceptible to bladder rupture and is typically only used for small parts.

In advanced TRP (Fig. 1) there is no need for an autoclave, which can be costly both to acquire and to maintain. Also, there is no need for a pneumatic system, which is prone to rupture and reduces the complexity of the design. Parts made using this processing technique are highly consolidated, which is desirable for high performance composites. This process also is amenable to robotic manufacturing.

Through detailed experimental characterization, a computational thermomechanical material model has been developed as a design tool for processing engineers. In addition, a method has been developed for this characterization process that can be used for other TRP materials.

2.1 Modelling

Hyperelastic materials can be modelled in a variety of ways. One of the empirically based approaches is the Mooney-Rivlin method. This method is accurate up to 200% strain [1] which will likely be outside the strain observed in TRP materials. This method is capable of modelling the large strain and nonlinear behaviour of incompressible materials like rubber. It consists of a series of parameters or curves used to fit with a specific material's test data. Thermo-mechanical material modelling can be conducted in a number of ways. Lion et al. [2] have developed an extension to the Mooney-Rivlin method to incorporate the thermomechanical response of the hyperelastic material. Lion's method considers a hydrostatic compression case where a specific compression modulus parameter is defined for the material. While realistic TRP units will have a complex stress state, the simplified hollow sphere used in the experiments has primarily hydrostatic stress. This provides a simple way to calibrate the initial material model. This method was selected for use in this project due to the needs for the simulation method to be robust, straight forward to parameterize, and simple to implement by utilizing a commercially available software and existing subroutines.

The development of an intuitive and accurate simulation approach is an important part of this initial study. The use of initial virtual experimentation methods allowed the evaluation of the tests for test method improvement and simplification. Throughout testing the experiments are correlated closely with

the virtual experiments for seamless computational material model development.

The virtual experiments make use of a fully coupled thermal-displacement analysis which is performed in Abaqus/Standard [7]. This implementation of thermomechanical analysis uses Newton's method with a nonsymmetric Jacobian matrix as shown in Equation 1. Here Δu and $\Delta \theta$ are the respective incremental displacement and temperature corrections, K_{ij} are the submatrices of the fully coupled Jacobian matrix, and R_u and R_θ are the respective mechanical and thermal residual vectors, [7].

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{uu} & K_{u\theta} \\ K_{\theta u} & K_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta u \\ \Delta \theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} R_u \\ R_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The elements used for the steel and aluminium parts are the C3D8RT, which are eight-node thermally-mechanically coupled hexahedral elements with reduced integration. Using reduced integration elements reduces the runtime by approximately 30% and has a negligible effect on the results.

In nearly incompressible materials, small changes in displacement can produce extremely large changes in pressure. Due to the incompressible nature of the rubber materials used in trapped rubber moulding, standard element formulations can result in an overly stiff model. Volumetric locking of incompressible materials is most severe when the material is highly confined. However, the changes in volume can be separated from the changes in shape as seen in Lion et al. [2]. The use of reduced integration can mitigate volumetric locking to some extent, but here hybrid reduced integration elements are used to further prevent locking. Because the Poisson's Ratio of the rubber is greater than 0.475 the hybrid formulation is used [11]. The hybrid element formulation in Abaqus utilizes the separation of change in volume and change in shape which results in the following expression for the rate of virtual work, equation 2 [11].

$$\begin{aligned} d\delta\bar{W} = \int_V \left\{ \delta\varepsilon : \mathbf{C} : \delta\varepsilon - \frac{1}{9K} (1 - \rho) \delta\varepsilon : \mathbf{C}^T : \mathbf{I} \mathbf{I} : \mathbf{C} : d\varepsilon + \delta\varepsilon : \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \mathbf{I} : d\varepsilon \right. \\ \left. - \frac{1}{3K} (1 - \rho) (\delta\hat{p} \mathbf{I} : \mathbf{C} : d\varepsilon + \delta\varepsilon : \mathbf{C}^T : \mathbf{I} d\hat{p}) - \frac{1}{K} (1 - \rho) \delta\hat{p} d\hat{p} \right. \\ \left. + \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \left[\left(\frac{\partial \delta \mathbf{u}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right)^T \cdot \frac{\partial d \mathbf{u}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} - 2 \delta \varepsilon \cdot d\varepsilon \right] \right\} dV \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

The analysis is run in single precision and the rubber material is modelled using C3D8HT (8-node thermally coupled hexahedral, trilinear displacement and temperature, hourglass control, hybrid, constant pressure) elements. Using hybrid elements for the rubber decreases the run time by over 30%, but results in an interface surface pressure that is approximately 1% lower than the simulation using the fully integrated elements.

There are two contact surfaces pairs in the full model, the contact between the inner surface of the aluminium mould and the outer surface of the rubber and the contact between the inner surface of the rubber and the outer surface of the steel sphere. In each contact pair, a surface to surface contact interaction is defined and no interference is allowed.

Additionally, thermal contact properties are required in order to simulate contact between the materials in the cavity mould simulation. For this, tabular thermal conductance is used, with only pressure-dependent data. This contact property uses pressure-dependency data where the conductance varies with the amount of pressure at the contact surface. This is used for both the contact surface between the aluminium and the rubber and the contact surface between the steel and the rubber. At this time no convection has been included in the model. During the preliminary simulations all the components remain in contact, therefore only a preliminary tabular gap conductance estimate has been included.

Conductance	Pressure
50	0
65	100
70	250

Table 1: Thermal Conductance Contact Property.

There are a number of parameters required for the material model of the various material included in the model. For the metallic components of the simulation, material properties were sourced from the material suppliers [9, 10]. These properties include conductivity, density, Young's Modulus, Poisson's Ratio, coefficient of thermal expansion, and specific heat index.

A Mooney-Rivlin rubber material model is used to characterize the hyperelastic response of the rubber material. Material properties are initialized using rubber supplier material data, Table 2. Using the approximation for a neo-Hookean material we can simplify the required constants to two for each increment of temperature, equations (3) and (4). One of the limitations of using the Mooney-Rivlin material model available in Abaqus/Standard is that it can only be used with large deformation theory. For the simulation of trapped rubber moulding with cavity shaped rubber pressure intensifiers, large deformation theory is not required. For a perfectly elastic material there is less than 2% change in the surface pressure when the small deformation theory results are compared with the large deformation theory.

Property	Value	Units
Young's Modulus	1.5x10 ⁹	Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.49	m/m
Density	1500	kg/m ³
Conductivity	1	S/m
Specific Heat Index	1050	J/K
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	0.00025	1/K

Table 2: Silicone Rubber Material (Simplified Elastic)

$$\lambda = 2 \cdot D_1 \quad (3)$$

$$\mu = 2 \cdot C_1 \quad (4)$$

Using these equations (3) and (4), an initial estimate for the Mooney-Rivlin coefficients can be determined by solving for the Lamé constants at room temperature. The Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio for this calculation can be found in Table 2. At room temperature these coefficients can be calculated based on the initial elasticity with small deformation. From this assumption equations (5) and (6) can be formulated. These can then be solved simultaneously to calculate the neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin coefficients (C_1 and D_1) seen in Table 3.

$$\nu = \frac{3 - 2 C_1 D_1}{6 + 2 C_1 D_1} \quad (5)$$

$$E = \frac{2 C_1 (6 C_1 + 6 D_1)}{2 C_1 + 2 D_1} \quad (6)$$

Property	Value	Units
Mooney-Rivlin (C_1)	2.50×10^8	Pa
Mooney-Rivlin (D_1)	8.05×10^{-11}	Pa
Density	1500	kg/m ³
Conductivity	1	S/m
Specific Heat Index	1050	J/K
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	0.00025	1/K

Table 3: Silicone Rubber Material (Hyperelastic)

For the silicone rubber material, the specific heat index is use with constant pressure. Initially the Mooney-Rivlin coefficients are held constant throughout the temperature range studied. However, when data is available, these Mooney-Rivlin coefficients can then be defined at an array of discrete temperatures for the material.

2.1.1 Temperature Change

The thermal transient is evaluated by placing the hollow rubber sphere in a two-part cavity mould. The rubber is effectively trapped between the outer surface of the steel sphere and the inner surface of the mould. Heat is then applied from the outside of the mould via flat aluminium plates under pressure containing electrical heating elements. Thermocouples applied to the external mould and the outer surface internal steel sphere are used to monitor the temperature change over time. Additionally, five thermocouples are distributed though the thickness of the rubber to capture the in-situ thermal transient with high accuracy. These thermocouples are moulded into the rubber material to achieve an accurate through thickness heating map in real time. The model is constructed to effectively represent the test apparatus including the full mould for simulation. Due to symmetry, only one eighth of the temperature change test is simulated. However, from the simulation a continuous gradient of temperature can be seen, while only discrete points are captured in the physical experiments. Due to the high thermal conductivity of the aluminium cavity mould, the interior temperature at the rubber surface can be assumed uniform. The simulations confirm this and show less than 0.0001 °C of difference in temperature on the inner cavity surface of the aluminium mould during the full simulation.

2.1.2 Pressure Change

The pressure transient is evaluated by placing the hollow rubber sphere in a two-part cavity mould. Heat is then applied from the outside of the mould via flat aluminium plates under pressure containing with electrical heating elements. A network of very thin pressure sensing devices are embedded in the mould between the outer surface of the rubber and the inner surface of the aluminium to obtain real-time pressure mapping of the surface during the test. The model is constructed to effectively represent the test apparatus including the full mould for simulation. Due to symmetry, only one eighth of the temperature change test is simulated. From the simulation CPRESS (normal force from contact pressure) is evaluated to compare with the experimental results [11].

2.2 Experimentation

The rubber elastomer used was chosen to be compatible with the cure cycle for Hexcel M21 epoxy prepreg system. The iterative testing and computational modelling framework is initialized with material models and then the characterization is validated and improved by experimental tests.

The experimental setup is designed and conducted to capture the volumetric change and resulting pressure via a series of material tests. These tests include: the change in temperature, and the change in surface pressure. The temperature and surface pressure apparatus consist of aluminium moulds with an internal steel sphere and the rubber material in a hollow sphere. The thermal expansion of the aluminium moulds and steel sphere is easily calculated during the cure cycle and thereby simplifies the

characterization of the rubber material.

3 RESULTS

The project is still ongoing and so any results presented here are preliminary. The focus thus far has been on the simulation of the virtual experiment, design of physical experiment and preliminary testing.

3.1 Modelling

A preliminary model has been constructed to simulate the experiments. Both temperature change and pressure change at the surfaces are simulated using the method described above. The initial model uses a single linear coefficient of thermal expansion for the rubber material, listed in Table 3.

3.1.1 Temperature Change

A preliminary temperature change simulation can be seen in Figure 2. Heat is applied on the top and bottom surfaces of the mould, in order to simulate the effects of placing the mould in a heated press. A linear ramp of temperature from 25 °C to 200 °C over 17.5 minutes, is used. From this simulation, it can be seen that the aluminium mould distributes the heat well despite only being heated from the two surfaces. Also, the temperature difference from the outside of the hollow rubber sphere to the inside is significant, ranging in this image from 38 °C to 62 °C (Fig. 2). This makes it very difficult to estimate the pressures resulting from the material expansion without a full computational analysis.

Figure 2: Temperature in rubber material

3.1.2 Pressure Change

A preliminary pressure change simulation can be seen in Figure 3. Heat is applied on the top and bottom surfaces of the mould, in order to simulate the effects of placing the mould in a heated press. A linear ramp of temperature from 25 °C to 200 °C over 17.5 minutes, is used. From this initial simulation it is apparent that very high pressures can be reached in a relatively short time within the temperature ranges for prepreg processing.

Figure 3: Rubber Surface Pressure (Pa) at timesteps indicated by exterior mould temperature

3.2 Experimentation

3.2.1 Materials

A CS25 condensation cure silicone rubber was purchased from Easy Composites Ltd. The combined rubber and catalyst were grey in colour, had the viscosity of 20000-26000 mPa.s at ambient temperature and had 1.04-1.14 g/cm³ density. The steel balls were purchased from Spekuma company and had the weight of 510 gram measuring 50 mm in diameter. Loctite hysol 9466 A&B adhesive was used to bond the spring pins and the holes in the 3-D printed PLA moulds. The processing time for the adhesive was 60 min, and the adhesive had the viscosity of 35 Pa.s and possessed the tensile strength of 32 MPa.

3.2.2 Processes

Two-part PLA moulds with spherical cavity of 60 mm in diameter were 3D-printed for use in casting the silicon rubber in the suspended steel ball. Two small holes were also designed at the bottom of each 3D-printed PLA moulds to be able to suspend the steel ball during the rubber casting by gluing (Loctite hysol 9466 A&B adhesive) four spring pins into the holes and subsequently resting the ball on the four spring pins.

The stoichiometric ratio of silicon rubber to catalyst (100 to 5 part by weight) was used, and the mix was degassed for the period of 3 minutes. Then the silicon rubber was poured gently into the 3 printed PLA mould with the suspended steel ball. The system was left to cure for 24 hours before demoulding and the whole demoulded part had the weight of 560 g.

4 CONCLUSIONS

There is very little current research in TRP. There was a substantial amount of research between 1975 and 1988 [2,3,4]. However, the high price of computational capacity and the low thermal conductivity of the rubber materials, at the time, stalled research. In the broader landscape of high-performance composite processing, there is an open need for autoclave alternatives that allow for faster throughput without sacrificing material performance. TRP allows more design freedom with more advanced shapes and less risk of processing failure while maintaining the possibility for custom distributions of pressures, custom distributions of temperatures and therefore high-quality consolidation and curing. The characterization process presented here demonstrates the need for computational simulation of the moulding process for accurate design of the processing mould and pressuring rubber material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Österlöf, “Modelling the viscoplastic properties of carbon black filled rubber”. Doctoral Thesis, KTH, 2016.
- [2] A. Lion, N. Diercks, and J. Caillard, “One the directional approach in constitutive modelling: A general thermomechanical framework and exact solutions for Mooney-Rivlin type elasticity in each direction”. *Int. J. of Solids and Structures*, **50** (14-15), 2013, pp. 2518-2526 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2013.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2013.04.002)).
- [3] D.N. Kemp, “Fixed-volume, trapped rubber molding method”. US4889668A Dec 26, 1989.
- [4] D.J. Barraclough, “Molding of composite materials”. US4624820A, Nov 25, 1986.
- [5] D.M. Hatch, R.J. Larsen, “High temperature consolidation process”. US4409048A, Oct 11, 1975.
- [6] Gilles Marckmann, Erwan Verron. Comparison of Hyperelastic Models for Rubber-Like Materials. *Rubber Chemistry and Technology*, American Chemical Society, 2006, 79, pp.835-858. 10.5254/1.3547969. hal-01004686v1
- [7] Mooney, M., 1940, A theory of large elastic deformation, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 11(9), pp. 582–592.
- [8] Rivlin, R. S., 1948, Large elastic deformations of isotropic materials. IV. Further developments of the general theory, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 241(835), pp. 379–397.
- [9] Metals Depot®, 6061-T6511 Aluminum bar, Metals Depot material properties data sheet, 2019
- [10] SKF Sweden AB, Material for bearing rings and rolling elements, SKF material properties data sheet, 2019
- [11] Dassault Systèmes ®, Abaqus Analysis User’s Manual 6.14, 2014